

DAVID P. CILIA

ON THE OCCURRENCE OF THE INVASIVE TERRESTRIAL
FLATWORM *OBAMA NUNGARA* CARBAYO, ÁLVAREZ-PRESAS,
JONES & RIUTORT, 2016 (*Platyhelminthes Geoplanidae*)
IN THE MALTESE ISLANDS

SUMMARY

The first Maltese record of a terrestrial planarian known to be highly invasive in Europe, *Obama nungara*, is presented. This species can be distinguished from other native and invasive flatworms through its dimensions and unique morphological characteristics.

Key words: terrestrial flatworm, Malta, alien species, invasive species.

RIASSUNTO

Nell'Arcipelago Maltese è stata recentemente individuata la presenza di una planaria terrestre estremamente invasiva in Europa, *Obama nungara*. Questa specie è distinguibile dalle altre specie native e invasive di vermi piatti grazie alle sue dimensioni e caratteristiche morfologiche uniche.

Parole chiave: verme piatto, Malta, specie aliena, specie invasiva

INTRODUCTION

Obama nungara Carbayo, Álvarez-Presas, Jones & Riutort, 2016 is a species of terrestrial flatworm (Platyhelminthes: Tricladida: Continenticola: Geoplanidae Stimpson, 1857) native to southern Brazil and Argentina (LAGO-BARCIA *et al.*, 2019) but which is now also widespread in Europe, possibly through passive anthropochorous dispersal with ornamental plants. It was recorded first in the UK in 2008 (CARBAYO *et al.*, 2016), then in Ireland in 2009 (JUSTINE *et al.*, 2014), in Spain in 2010 (CARBAYO *et al.*, 2016), in Italy in 2012 (CARBAYO *et al.*, 2016), in

France in 2013 (JUSTINE *et al.*, 2014), in Switzerland in 2014 (JUSTINE *et al.*, 2020), in the Netherlands in 2016 (ALDRED, 2016), in Belgium in 2017 (SOORS *et al.*, 2019), in Slovakia in 2021 (ČAPKA & ČEJKA, 2021), in Croatia in 2021 (MORI *et al.*, 2023), in Austria and Germany in 2022 (JUSTINE *et al.*, 2022), and in Greece, Slovenia, Türkiye, and Hungary in 2023 (MORI *et al.*, 2023, LAZÁNYI *et al.*, 2024). In this note, the first record from the Maltese Islands is presented.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

One specimen discovered by Denis Magro in the garden of a private residence, Triq il-Parroċċa, Qrendi (Malta) on 20.XI.2023 was made available to the author for study. The specimen was partially coiled up in damp soil on the roots of *Monstera deliciosa* Liebm. Colouration, morphometrics and behaviour of the individual were observed over the course of two days. Subsequently, fixation in near boiling water and preservation in 95% ethanol solution was effected. The specimen is deposited in the collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Mdina (Malta).

RESULTS

The colouration of *O. nungara* observed on the dorsum of the studied specimen consist of dark brown pigmentation over a lighter brown ground colour, with a marbled pattern intensifying towards the dorsolateral margins (Fig. 1), corresponding to the dark morph elaborated upon in JUSTINE *et al.* (2020). The ventral side is a pale brownish grey, lighter at the mid-line and darker with a purplish tinge towards the margins. In cross-section, the planarian is narrowly elliptical, with the dorsum more convex than the sole. The junction between the dorsum and the sole is acutely angulated. The anterior end of the vaguely lanceolate planarian tapers gently to a point

Fig. 1 — The planarian *Obama nungara* Carbayo, Álvarez-Presas, Jones & Riutort, 2016; specimen from Qrendi, Malta. Photographed by Denis Magro, 20.XI.2023.

while the posterior end does so more abruptly, resulting in the cephalic region being the more pointed, acutely angular end. Eye spots are not immediately evident to the naked eye, but their contour is evident under a stereomicroscope. Fully extended, the planarian measured 63mm long and 5mm wide (35mm long and 10mm wide when contracted).

DISCUSSION

O. nungara was only distinguished from its congener *Obama marmorata* (Schultze & Müller, 1857) through histological and molecular characters very recently (CARBAYO *et al.*, 2016); however, morphological features can also be used for differentiating between the two - *O. nungara* reaches a length of about 70mm, while *O. marmorata* may attain up to 100mm and is usually of a lighter colour.

Three other terrestrial planarians have been recorded for Malta by LANFRANCO (1970; 1975), all from anthropogenic habitats, and all three can be differentiated fairly easily from *O. nungara*. Two (presumably native) species, *Microplana terrestris* (Müller, 1773) and *Rhynchodemus sylvaticus* (Leidy, 1851) (recorded as *R. bilineatus* (Mecznikow)) are by far the smallest of the lot, with adults of the former attaining a length of up to 20mm and those of the latter of around 30mm. The body of *R. sylvaticus* is oval or round in cross-section, with a pair of dark brown striae on a paler background running along its dorsum and two distinct black eye spots on its anterior end. On the other hand, adults of the allochthonous *Bipalium kewense* Moseley, 1878 may easily grow up to 200mm. No further records of Geoplanidae could be traced for Malta.

The passive anthropochorous dispersal of animals outside of their native range through the horticultural trades is a well-documented phenomenon, with case studies from Malta presented in e.g., LANFRANCO (1975), BARBARA & SCHEMBRI (2008), MIFSUD & DACCORDI (2019), MIFSUD (2020), CILIA *et al.* (2022), etc. This mode of introduction is also the probable scenario for the current record (see SOORS *et al.*, 2019; MORI *et al.*, 2022). A number of such incidents develop into fully fledged invasions of serious agricultural or ecological concern, as demonstrated by MIFSUD (1995) and CAMILLERI *et al.* (2022). Some of the (at least) 18 species of terrestrial flatworms known to have been introduced in Europe (ÁLVAREZ-PRESAS *et al.*, 2014; JUSTINE *et al.*, 2020) potentially fall within this category. All such flatworms are externally distinct from *O. nungara*: representatives of *Bipalium* and *Diversibipalium* (including *B. kewense* above) possess flattened heads of a characteristic semilunar to semicircular shape, with discernible 'neck' regions; *Caenoplana* spp. grow up to 150mm and exhibit a light dorsal stripe contrasting strongly with the dark dorsum; *Arthurdendyus triangulatus* (Dendy, 1894) is thin, elongated and coffee-coloured with a very pale and well-delineated margin,

and can grow up to 200mm; *Marionfyfea advector* Jones & Sluys, 2016 only grows to around 10mm; *Dolichoplana striata* Moseley, 1877 is elongated and yellowish, with four dark brown dorsolateral stripes, and reaches a length of around 100mm but a width of only around 1mm when extended; *Australopacifica atrata* (Steel, 1897) grows up to 30mm and displays defined ventrolateral stripes; *Kontikia ventrolineata* (Dendy, 1892) possesses two stripes on both the ventral and the dorsal aspects and grows to about 15mm; finally, *Platydemus manokwari* De Beauchamp, 1963, attains a size and colouration comparable to that of *O. nungara*, but may be distinguished by prominent eye spots and one unmistakable light stripe bisecting its dorsum. Pictures in colour of several species mentioned above are provided by JONES (2005), ÁLVAREZ-PRESAS *et al.* (2014), and JUSTINE *et al.* (2014).

Tolerance to a wide range of temperatures and high rates of disturbance, together with a wide spectrum of prey species, bolster the invasive potential of *O. nungara* and contribute to its high ecological impact. Populations of indigenous oligochaetes and pulmonate gastropods are likely to be affected negatively due to predation by *O. nungara*. In fact, JUSTINE *et al.* (2020) state that it is ‘the most important invasive species of land flatworm in Europe’. Its range in Europe is likely to keep expanding eastwards in the immediate future (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 — The eastward spread of *O. nungara* through Europe. Each shade represents first records for countries at five-year intervals (black: 2005–2010; dark grey: 2011–2015; grey: 2016–2020; light grey: 2021–[2025]). The Maltese Islands are indicated by an arrow.

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Author's Address. D.P. CILIA, Mużew Nazzjonali tal-Istorja Naturali / National Museum of Natural History, Vilhena Palace, St. Publius Square, Mdina, MDN 1011, Malta; email: dpcilia@gmail.com [0000-0001-8437-8913].